

THE WAYS OF EXPRESSING PRESENT SUBJUNCTIVE MOOD

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Abstract. This article discusses the types of subjunctive mood in American English and the grammatical and lexical units which are used to express them.

Keywords: subjunctive mood, subjunctive I, subjunctive II, wishes, construction.

Expressing wishes and desires is an important aspect of human communication, allowing speakers to express situations that are not currently realized, but are hoped for, desired, or imagined. This thesis analyzes the 2 categories and subcategories of the Subjunctive mood in American English, the tenses, auxiliary verbs, and constructions used with examples in expressing them.

The issue of subjunctive mood can be approached from two perspectives: American and British English, but we will analyze the former one. The American perspective provides a comprehensive overview of the topic, while the British approach focuses on specific areas. According to information from speakasap.com [1] and grammarway.com [2], the subjunctive mood in American English is divided into 2 types depending on the participation of auxiliary verbs:

- a) Subjunctive I
- b) Subjunctive II

Subjunctive I or the synthetic form of the subjunctive mood is formed with the help of special forms of the semantic verb (with the help of endings or suffixes). In Old English there were a large number of special forms of verbs used for the subjunctive mood. However, they were significantly simplified or lost and in modern English, there are only two forms of this mood: The Present Subjunctive and The Past Subjunctive [3].

The Present Subjunctive I can be expressed in several ways. The first way is by using the construction *It is/was + adjective + that + ...* , in this case the adjective used must have a meaning that indicates the importance of the action, and the verb of the following sentence must be in the **infinitive** form.

- *It is vital that everybody **come** 10 minutes before the exam.*

The Present Subjunctive I form is also used after verbs such as *insist, suggest, recommend, order, command, ask, demand, propose, request, advise and urge* [4].

- *We suggest that the meeting **be** postponed.*
- *The manager asked that I **be** present at the meeting.*

To make a negative sentence the particle NOT must be used before the bare infinitive.

- *I recommend that you **not use** your phone during the exam time.*

We also use the Present Subjunctive I form in imperative sentences, and in many cases these sentences are invariable conjunctions that express wishes and hopes.

- ***Rest in peace! Be it so! Bless you!***

According to englishmaria.com, Present Subjunctive is used to express wishes, strong wishes or advice with “I’d rather” and set phrases.

Wishes [5].

- *May all your dreams **come** true!*

Strong wishes or advice with “I’d rather”

- ***I’d rather you quit cursing. or I’d rather you not curse in here.***

Set phrases.

- *Let it **be**! God **bless** you!* [6]

The examples given above relate to business language, for the colloquial variant native speakers may well (and most likely will) use the construction should + infinitive. Everything is the same as we considered above, only with should (except for set expressions). [7]

- *It is vital that everybody **should come** 10 minutes before the exam.*
- *We suggest that the meeting **should be** postponed.*
- *The manager asked that I **should be** present at the meeting.*

Past Subjunctive I - in this type, verbs are used in the **past tense** and express unreal actions in the present. As the rules are not without exceptions, the important thing to remember is that the verb to be is always used in the form of **were** in these types of sentences.

- *If I **were** you, I would buy a new housing*
- *If I **came**, he would lend me some money*

- *I wish you were home*
- *I wish I knew how to solve this problem*
- *It’s high time you went home*

According to englishmaria.com, Past Subjunctive I can be used in subordinate sentences following conjunctions like “as if”, “as though”, “if only” to indicate wishes that are unreal or regrets.

- *He is talking to his dog as if it understood him*
- *If only I were there to solve their problem*
- *Paul is speaking as though he were the manager*

Although the site grammarway.com separates only two forms of the Subjunctive I (The Present Subjunctive and The Past Subjunctive), speakasap.com mentions its third form - The Past Perfect Subjunctive. This form describes unreal events of the past and the action of this mood obviously did not occur in the past. It may be a missed opportunity. In order to form The Past Perfect Subjunctive “had + Verb in past participle or with suffix -d/-ed” is used. We use the third form:

- ✓ When we talk about an unreal action that relates exclusively to the past.
- ✓ The third type of conditional sentence. The third type of conditional: If + Past Perfect, would have + III form of the verb (if correct, then the ending is -ed, if incorrect, then the third column in the table of irregular verbs).
- ✓ In sentences with the *I wish* construction, when we talk about an unreal event in the past [8].

- *She seems as if she hadn’t slept for three days*
- *I wish you had come on time*
- *She would have passed the exam if she had studied harder*

The subjunctive mood serves as a powerful grammatical tool that expresses wishes, hypothetical situations, and uncertainties in English, enriching the language's expressive capabilities. The subjunctive mood not only conveys nuances of desire and doubt but also reflects the speaker's attitude towards the action being described, highlighting its importance in effective communication.

Reference:

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